

Lyapunov-type inequalities for higher order difference equations with anti-periodic boundary conditions

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Abstract. In this paper, some new Lyapunov-type inequalities for higher order difference equations with anti-periodic boundary conditions are established. The obtained results are used to obtain the lower bounds for the eigenvalues of corresponding equations.

Keywords: Difference equation; Anti-periodic boundary conditions; Lyapunov-type inequalities.

1. Introduction

The standard Lyapunov-type inequality [4] is useful in many applications, including eigenvalue problems, oscillation theory, disconjugacy. Although there are many literatures on the Lyapunov-type inequality for various classes of differential equations [1,3,6,8,9], there is not much done for the difference equations.

In 1983, Cheng [2] first established the following Lyapunov-type inequality which is a discrete analogue of the classical Lyapunov-type inequality:

If the second order difference equation

$$\begin{cases} \Delta^2 x(n) + q(n)x(n+1) = 0, \\ x(a) = x(b) = 0, x(n) \not\equiv 0, \quad n \in \mathbb{Z}[a, b], \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

has a nonzero solution, then

$$F(b-a) \sum_{n=a}^{b-2} q(n) \geq 4,$$

where

$$F(m) = \begin{cases} \frac{m^2 - 1}{m}, & \text{if } m - 1 \text{ is even,} \\ m, & \text{if } m - 1 \text{ is odd,} \end{cases}$$

$a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $\mathbb{Z}[a, b] = \{a, a+1, \dots, b-1, b\}$. Some other related results about discrete Lyapunov-type inequalities can be found in [5,7,10].

In this paper, we will consider the following difference equation

$$\Delta(|\Delta^m x(n)|^{p-2} \Delta^m x(n)) + r(n)|x(n)|^{p-2} x(n) = 0, (1.2)$$

with the anti-periodic boundary conditions

$$\Delta^i x(a) + \Delta^i x(b) = 0, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, m, (1.3)$$

where $x(n) \not\equiv 0, n \in \mathbb{Z}[a, b], m \in \mathbb{N}, p > 1, r(n)$ is a real-valued function defined on \mathbb{Z} .

Furthermore, we will establish a new Lyapunov-type inequality for the following equation

$$|\Delta^m x(n)|^{p-2} \Delta^m x(n) + r(n)|x(n)|^{p-2} x(n) = 0, \quad (1.4)$$

with the anti-periodic boundary conditions

$$\Delta^i x(a) + \Delta^i x(b) + \Delta^i x(c) = 0, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1, \quad (1.5)$$

where $x(n) \neq 0, n \in \mathbb{Z}[a, c], a < b < c, m \in \mathbb{N}, p > 1, r(n)$ is a real-valued function defined on \mathbb{Z} .

2. Main results

In this section, we give two main results and some corollaries.

Theorem 2.1. If (1.2) has a nonzero solution $x(n)$ satisfying the anti-periodic boundary conditions (1.3), then

$$\sum_{n=a}^{b-1} |r(n)| \geq 2 \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \right)^{m(p-1)}.$$

Proof. For $x(a) + x(b) = 0$, then

$$\begin{aligned} x(n) &= x(n) - \frac{1}{2}[x(a) + x(b)] \\ &= \frac{1}{2}[x(n) - x(a)] - \frac{1}{2}[x(b) - x(n)] \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=a}^{n-1} \Delta x(k) - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=n}^{b-1} \Delta x(k). \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, we have

$$|x(n)| \leq \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=a}^{n-1} |\Delta x(k)| + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=n}^{b-1} |\Delta x(k)| = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta x(k)|,$$

then

$$|x(n)| \leq \frac{1}{2} (b-a)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left(\sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta x(k)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \quad (2.1)$$

by Hölder's inequality, where $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$.

Using the boundary conditions (1.3), we obtain

$$|\Delta^i x(n)| \leq \frac{1}{2} (b-a)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left(\sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^{i+1} x(k)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \quad (2.2)$$

$$|\Delta^i x(n)|^p \leq \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^p (b-a)^{\frac{p}{q}} \sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^{i+1} x(k)|^p,$$

$$\sum_{n=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^i x(n)|^p \leq \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^p (b-a)^p \sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^{i+1} x(k)|^p,$$

$$\left(\sum_{n=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^i x(n)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \leq \frac{1}{2} (b-a) \left(\sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^{i+1} x(k)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}. \quad (2.3)$$

Combining inequalities (2.1) and (2.3), we have

$$\begin{aligned} |x(n)| &\leq \frac{1}{2}(b-a)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left(\sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta x(k)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2}(b-a)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^{m-1} \left(\sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^m x(k)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^m (b-a)^{m-\frac{1}{p}} \left(\sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^m x(k)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \end{aligned}$$

therefore

$$|x(n)|^{p-1} \leq \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{m(p-1)} (b-a)^{\left(m-\frac{1}{p}\right)(p-1)} \left(\sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^m x(k)|^p \right)^{\frac{p-1}{p}}. \quad (2.4)$$

Moreover, by the boundary conditions (1.3), we have the following equality

$$\sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^m x(k)|^p = \sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^m x(k+1)|^p.$$

Combining inequalities (2.2) and (2.4),

$$\begin{aligned} |x(n)|^{p-1} |\Delta^{m-1} x(n+1)| &\leq \left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{m(p-1)} (b-a)^{\left(m-\frac{1}{p}\right)(p-1)} \left(\sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^m x(k+1)|^p \right)^{\frac{p-1}{p}} \\ &\quad \cdot \frac{1}{2} (b-a)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left(\sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^m x(k+1)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ &= C \sum_{k=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^m x(k+1)|^p, \end{aligned}$$

where $C = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^{m(p-1)}$.

Multiplying (1.2) by $\Delta^{m-1} x(n+1)$ and summing the obtained equation from a to $b-1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^m x(n+1)|^p &= \sum_{n=a}^{b-1} r(n) |x(n)|^{p-2} x(n) \Delta^{m-1} x(n+1) \\ &\leq \sum_{n=a}^{b-1} |r(n)| |x(n)|^{p-1} |\Delta^{m-1} x(n+1)| \\ &\leq C \left(\sum_{n=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^m x(n+1)|^p \right) \sum_{n=a}^{b-1} |r(n)|, \end{aligned}$$

Noting that $\Delta^m x(a) + \Delta^m x(b) = 0$ and $x(n) \neq 0, n \in \mathbb{Z}[a, b]$, we have

$$\sum_{n=a}^{b-1} |\Delta^m x(n+1)|^p > 0,$$

therefore,

$$\sum_{n=a}^{b-1} |r(n)| \geq 2 \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \right)^{m(p-1)}.$$

The proof is complete. \square

Theorem 2.2. If (1.4) has a nonzero solution $x(n)$ satisfying the anti-periodic boundary conditions (1.5), then

$$\sum_{n=a}^{c-1} |r(n)|^q \geq \frac{3^{mp}}{2^{mp} (c-a)^{mp-1}},$$

where $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$.

Proof. Since $x(a) + x(b) + x(c) = 0$, we have

$$x(n) = x(n) - \frac{1}{3}[x(a) + x(b) + x(c)].$$

Casen $\in \mathbb{Z}[a, b]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} x(n) &= \frac{1}{3}[x(n) - x(a)] - \frac{1}{3}[x(b) - x(n)] - \frac{1}{3}[x(c) - x(n)] \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=a}^{n-1} \Delta x(k) - \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=n}^{b-1} \Delta x(k) - \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=n}^{c-1} \Delta x(k) \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=a}^{n-1} \Delta x(k) - \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=n}^{b-1} \Delta x(k) - \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=n}^{b-1} \Delta x(k) - \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=b}^{c-1} \Delta x(k). \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} |x(n)| &\leq \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=a}^{c-1} |\Delta x(k)| + \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=n}^{b-1} |\Delta x(k)| \\ &\leq \frac{2}{3} \sum_{k=a}^{c-1} |\Delta x(k)|. \end{aligned}$$

Casen $\in \mathbb{Z}[b, c]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} x(n) &= \frac{1}{3}[x(n) - x(a)] + \frac{1}{3}[x(n) - x(b)] - \frac{1}{3}[x(c) - x(n)] \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=a}^{n-1} \Delta x(k) + \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=b}^{n-1} \Delta x(k) - \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=n}^{c-1} \Delta x(k) \\ &= \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=a}^{b-1} \Delta x(k) + \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=b}^{n-1} \Delta x(k) + \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=b}^{n-1} \Delta x(k) - \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=n}^{c-1} \Delta x(k). \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$|x(n)| \leq \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=a}^{c-1} |\Delta x(k)| + \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=b}^{n-1} |\Delta x(k)| \leq \frac{2}{3} \sum_{k=a}^{c-1} |\Delta x(k)|.$$

Thus, we have

$$|x(n)| \leq \frac{2}{3} \sum_{k=a}^{c-1} |\Delta x(k)| \leq \frac{2}{3} (c-a)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left(\sum_{k=a}^{c-1} |\Delta x(k)|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

for $n \in \mathbb{Z}[a, c]$. The rest of the proof is similar to the Theorem 2.1, we omit it. \square

Corollary 2.3. Consider the following eigenvalue problem

$$\begin{cases} \Delta(|\Delta^m x(n)|^{p-2} \Delta^m x(n)) + \lambda r(n) |x(n)|^{p-2} x(n) = 0, \\ \Delta^i x(a) + \Delta^i x(b) = 0, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, m, \end{cases}$$

where $x(n) \neq 0$, $n \in \mathbb{Z}[a, b]$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $p > 1$, $r(n)$ is a real-valued function defined on \mathbb{Z} , then we have

$$|\lambda| \geq 2 \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \right)^{m(p-1)} \left(\sum_{n=a}^{b-1} |r(n)| \right)^{-1}.$$

Corollary 2.4. Consider the following eigenvalue problem

$$\begin{cases} |\Delta^m x(n)|^{p-2} \Delta^m x(n) + \eta r(n) |x(n)|^{p-2} x(n) = 0, \\ \Delta^i x(a) + \Delta^i x(b) + \Delta^i x(c) = 0, \quad i = 0, 1, \dots, m-1, \end{cases}$$

where $x(n) \neq 0$, $n \in \mathbb{Z}[a, c]$, $a < b < c$, $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $r(n)$ is a real-valued function defined on \mathbb{Z} , $p > 1$, $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, then we have

$$|\eta| \geq \frac{3^{m(p-1)}}{2^{m(p-1)} (c-a)^{(m-\frac{1}{p})(p-1)} (\sum_{n=a}^{c-1} |r(n)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}}}.$$

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